

PERCEPTIONS AND OPINIONS ON THE INTEGRATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN RESEARCH AND ACADEMICS: BASIS FOR POLICY DEVELOPMENT

Ruel M. Flores

Research and Marketing Department, Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. Cauayan City, Isabela, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15619114>

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the perceptions and opinions on the integration of artificial intelligence (ai) in research and academics: basis for policy development. A descriptive survey was employed to collect data from 210 respondents. Findings revealed a generally positive outlook on AI's potential to enhance research efficiency and effectiveness. However, concerns about data privacy, ethical implications, and the need for adequate training were identified. Key findings include the perceived benefits of AI in data analysis, decision-making, and research dissemination. Beyond institutional impact, the study highlights how AI integration can advance the local community by fostering greater access to innovative research outputs and educational resources. This outreach is expected to benefit local stakeholders, particularly through collaborative projects that address community-specific challenges. The study provides a foundation for crafting policies and guidelines to effectively integrate AI into research and academic practices while mitigating potential risks. Recommendations include developing a comprehensive AI integration framework, investing in faculty development, establishing an ethics committee, and allocating necessary resources to ensure AI-driven advancements contribute positively to both academic and community development.

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, AI integration, higher education, research, academic endeavors, perceptions, attitudes, students, faculty, policy, guidelines, ethics, data privacy.*

INTRODUCTION

Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan (OLPCC) has a rich history of adapting to educational advancements since its establishment in 1956. Evolving from a humble secondary school into a respected institution in central Isabela, OLPCC has consistently championed quality Catholic education while embracing progress. Today, it stands as a testament to both tradition and innovation, featuring modern facilities, a highly skilled faculty, and a curriculum deeply rooted in Christ's teachings (Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc., n.d.).

In the contemporary educational landscape, technological advancements, particularly **artificial intelligence (AI)**, are reshaping various industries, including education. Though its origins trace back to the 1950s, AI has undergone significant evolution, now boasting sophisticated algorithms capable of learning and adapting (Russell & Norvig, 2010). The transformative potential of AI in education has captured global attention, prompting widespread interest in its integration into academic practices.

While AI offers considerable promise in delivering personalized learning experiences, automating administrative tasks, and enhancing research efficiency, its integration into research and academic tasks at institutions like OLPCC remains in its early stages. Understanding the perspectives of academic heads, research advisers, and college students regarding AI integration is crucial for Our Lady of the Pillar College Cauayan, Inc.'s strategic planning, curriculum development, and refinement of research methodologies.

Currently, students at Our Lady of the Pillar College Cauayan, Inc. are not authorized to use AI for their research endeavors. However, recognizing the widespread adoption of AI across various sectors, it's imperative to explore its potential within the college's academic framework. This study aims to gather insights from stakeholders to inform the development of policies and guidelines for AI utilization in research at Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. Through surveys and direct engagement with stakeholders, this study seeks to gain a comprehensive understanding of the OLPCC community's perspectives on AI. The findings will form the foundation for future decisions regarding AI integration, ensuring OLPCC remains at the forefront of modern education, equipped to provide optimal opportunities for its students and staff.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the perceptions and opinions on the integration of artificial intelligence (ai) in research and academics: basis for policy development.

More specifically, the study answered the following questions:

1. What are the demographic profiles of the academic heads, research advisers and students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc. in terms of:

- 1.1. Research Adviser/Academic Head
 - 1.1.1. Age
 - 1.1.2. Sex
 - 1.1.3. Years of service
 - 1.1.4. Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.1.5. Familiarity to Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools in Research
- 1.2. Student Researcher
 - 1.2.1. Age
 - 1.2.2. Sex
 - 1.2.3. Academic Year Level
 - 1.2.4. Field of Study or Specialization
 - 1.2.5. Familiarity to Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools in Research
2. What is the initial experience and learning process of academic heads, research advisers and students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc. when it comes to using Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools within the research setting?
3. What are the perceptions, thinking, and opinions of the academic heads, research advisers and college students on the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of:
 - 3.1. Usability of AI tools
 - 3.2. Effectiveness of AI in aiding research
 - 3.3. Ease of learning and adaptability to AI methodologies
 - 3.4. Accuracy and veracity of AI-driven outcomes.
4. What are the advantages and challenges associated with incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) into academic research at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc., in terms of:
 - 4.1. Instruction
 - 4.2. Implementation
 - 4.3. Evaluation
5. What are the perceived changes in roles and responsibilities of academic heads, research advisers and college students in the context of AI integration into academic research?
6. What policies and guidelines could be crafted to facilitate the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into academic research processes at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc.?

METHODOLOGY

Method of Research Used

This study employed the descriptive survey method. Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon, answering "what," "where," "when," and "how" questions. This approach allowed the researchers to gather and interpret existing facts regarding the perceptions and opinions on the integration of artificial intelligence (ai) in research and academics: basis for policy development.

Prior to data collection, formal consent was obtained from the administration of Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc., allowing the institution to be mentioned by name in this study. All procedures were conducted in strict adherence to data privacy regulations and ethical guidelines for research involving human participants.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents for this study comprised five (05) academic heads, ten (10) research advisers, and one hundred ninety-five (195) research students enrolled in research writing courses across various college programs during the Academic Year 2023-2024. The distribution of respondents is as follows:

Academic Heads	5	0.02%
Research Advisers	10	0.05%
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology	06	0.03%
Bachelor of Science in Accountancy and Information System	42	0.20%
Bachelor of Elementary/Secondary Education	21	0.10%
Bachelor of Science in Criminology	37	0.18%
Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management	06	0.03%
Bachelor of Science in Computer Engineering	06	0.03%
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration	24	0.11%
Bachelor of Science in Nursing	53	0.25%

Data Gathering Instruments

The researcher used constructed questionnaire to determine the perceptions and opinions on the integration of artificial intelligence (ai) in research and academics: basis for policy development.

Data Gathering Procedures

All data gathered were kept confidential as promised by the researcher to the respondents. All data collected were carefully studied for reliability and consistency to avail the essential responses relevant to the study.

The researcher followed the steps and procedures systematically in gathering the most important data:

1. A letter of permission was requested to conduct the study.
2. Questionnaires were constructed and distributed to the Senior High School Academic head, Research Teachers and students enrolled in research subjects to validate the questionnaire.
3. The research questionnaires were distributed and administered to the respondents.
4. The questionnaires were retrieved, analyzed, and interpreted.

Statistical Tools

In answering the problems of the study, the researcher used the following statistical tools in organizing and interpreting the data gathered.

Frequency Count. This tool was used to determine the number of cases under category. It will determine the frequency of a particular result in a given statistical survey.

Mean. This tool was used to determine the average perceptions, thinking, and opinions of the respondents using the formula:

Where:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

= mean

= summation of the product of the value and its corresponding frequency account

$$N = \sum X$$

= the number of respondents

Percentage. This tool was used to determine the proportion of share in relation to a whole.

Likert Scale. It is a psychometric scale commonly used in questionnaires to measure attitudes, opinions, or perceptions. It typically consists of a series of statements to which respondents indicate their level of agreement or disagreement on a multi-point scale, usually ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." The scale includes 4 points, allowing for a nuanced response that captures the intensity of respondents' feelings or attitudes toward the given statements.

Option	Interpretation
4	Strongly Agree
3	Agree
2	Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

RESULTS

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Age

Age	Research Adviser		Academic Head		Student Researcher		Total	
	f	%	F	%	F	%	f	%
18 – 22	0	0	0	0	187	95.9	187	89.0
23 – 27	0	0	0	0	7	3.6	7	3.3
28 – 32	2	20	0	0	1	0.5	3	1.4
33 – 37	5	50	0	0	0	0	5	2.4
38 – 42	2	20	0	0	0	0	2	1.0
43 – above	1	10	5	100	0	0	6	2.9
Total	10	100	5	100	195	100	210	100

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Sex

Sex	Research Adviser		Academic Head		Student Researcher		Total	
	f	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Male	9	90	2	40	55	28.2	66	31.4
Female	1	10	3	60	140	71.8	144	68.6
Total	10	100	5	100	195	100	210	100

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Familiarity to Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools in Research

Familiarity	Research Adviser		Academic Head		Student Researcher		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	f	%
Not familiar at all	0	0	1	20	5	2.6	6	2.9
Somewhat familiar	3	30	3	60	53	27.2	59	28.1
Moderately familiar	6	60	1	20	110	56.4	117	55.7
Very familiar	1	10	0	0	27	13.8	28	13.3
Total	10	100	5	100	195	100	210	100
Mean	2.80 Moderately familiar		2.00 Somewhat familiar		2.82 Moderately familiar		2.80 Moderately familiar	

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to
Years in Academic Field of Academic Heads and Research Advisers

Years in Academic Field	Research Adviser		Academic Head		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
1 – 5	3	30	0	0	3	20.0
6 – 10	1	10	1	20	2	13.3
11 – 15	4	40	0	0	4	26.7
16 – 20	1	10	2	40	3	20.0
21 – 25	1	10	1	20	2	13.3
26 and above	0	0	1	20	1	6.7
Total	10	100	5	100	15	100

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Highest
Educational Attainment of Academic Heads and Research Advisers

Educational Attainment	Research Adviser		Academic Head		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
Bachelor's Degree	4	40	0	0	4	26.7
Master's Degree	6	60	4	80	10	66.7
Doctorate	0	0	1	20	1	6.7
Total	10	100	5	100	15	100

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Academic
Year Level of Students Researchers

Year Level	Frequency	Percent
Third Year	80	41.0
Fourth Year	114	58.5
Fifth Year	1	0.5
Total	195	100

Table 7
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Field of
Study or Specialization of Students Researchers

Specialization	Frequency	Percent
BS in Accountancy	26	13.3
BS in Accounting Information System	16	8.2
BS in Business Administration	24	12.3
Bachelor of Secondary Education	16	8.2
Bachelor of Elementary Education	05	2.6
BS in Computer Engineering	06	3.1
BS in Criminology	37	19.0
BS in Information Technology	06	3.1
BS in Nursing	53	27.2

BS in Hospitality Management	06	3.1
Total	195	100

Table 8
Mean Scores of the Initial Experience and Learning of the Academic Heads, Research Advisers, and College Students about Artificial Intelligence (Ai) Tools within the Research Setting of the Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc.

	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. My first exposure to AI tools in research was through online resources at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc.	2.60	A	2.60	A	2.41	D	2.42	D
2. My peers or colleagues, classmates were the first to introduce me to the concept of using AI tools for research at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc.	2.00	D	2.80	A	2.73	A	2.70	A
3. I was first introduced to AI tools in research through personal exploration outside of the college's curriculum.	3.30	SA	3.00	A	2.82	A	2.85	A
4. My interest in AI tools for research was sparked by global trends and discussions, not directly related to Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc.	3.00	A	3.40	SA	2.82	A	2.84	A
5. At Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc., I noticed a growing interest among academic heads/students/research advisers in integrating AI tools into their personal research projects.	2.80	A	3.00	A	2.79	A	2.80	A
6. External workshops, seminars, or courses (not provided by Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc.) were my main introduction to AI tools in research.	3.00	A	2.60	A	2.54	A	2.57	A
7. During my initial encounters with AI in research, I felt a need for more structured guidance and training.	3.00	A	2.80	A	2.99	A	2.99	A
8. My first impressions of using AI tools in research were that they were complex and challenging.	2.80	A	2.60	A	2.93	A	2.92	A
9. Collaborative group activities or team projects outside of the college's formal curriculum were where I initially encountered AI tools in research.	2.90	A	2.20	D	2.75	A	2.74	A
10. I believe that incorporating AI tools in research can significantly benefit academic projects, even if it's not a formal part of the curriculum at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc.	3.20	A	2.80	A	3.09	A	3.09	A
Category Mean	2.86	A	2.78	A	2.79	A	2.79	A

Table 9
Mean Scores of the Perceptions of the Academic Heads, Research Advisers and College Students to the Integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Academic Research in terms of Usability of AI Tools

PERCEPTIONS	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The user interfaces of AI tools in academic research are intuitive and easy to navigate.	2.80	A	3.40	SA	2.93	A	2.94	A
2. The features provided by AI tools enhance the usability of the tools for academic research.	3.00	A	3.20	A	2.99	A	3.00	A
3. The design of AI tools contributes to a positive user experience in academic research settings.	3.10	A	3.00	A	3.04	A	3.04	A
4. Navigation within AI research tools is straightforward and user-friendly.	3.10	A	3.20	A	3.01	A	3.01	A
5. The overall usability of AI tools significantly impacts its effectiveness in academic research.	3.00	A	3.20	A	3.04	A	3.04	A
Category Mean	3.00	A	3.20	A	3.00	A	3.01	A

Table 10
Mean Scores of the Thinking of the Academic Heads, Research Advisers and College Students to the Integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Academic Research in Terms of Usability of AI Tools

THINKING	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The features of AI tools align well with the academic research needs of users.	2.90	A	3.20	A	2.98	A	2.99	A
2. The usability of AI tools is a critical factor in determining its practicality for academic research.	2.90	A	3.20	A	2.97	A	2.98	A
3. AI tools have the potential to modernize and optimize research processes.	3.00	A	3.40	SA	3.08	A	3.09	A
4. The design and interface of AI tools contribute positively to the thinking and decision-making aspects of academic research.	3.10	A	3.40	SA	2.99	A	3.01	A
5. The ease of learning and adapting to the functionalities of AI tools is vital for its effective use in academic research.	3.20	A	3.20	A	3.07	A	3.08	A
Category Mean	3.02	A	3.28	SA	3.02	A	3.03	A

Table 11
Mean scores of the opinions of the academic heads, research advisers and college students to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of Usability of AI Tools

OPINIONS	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. I believe that user-friendly AI tools positively influence the overall productivity of academic research.	3.30	SA	3.00	A	3.09	A	3.10	A
2. The usability of AI tools plays a significant role in shaping researchers' attitudes towards their adoption.	3.20	A	2.80	A	2.95	A	2.96	A
3. The integration of AI tools with intuitive interfaces enhances the quality of academic research.	2.90	A	2.80	A	2.96	A	2.95	A
4. The practicality and ease of use of AI tools greatly influence its acceptance among researchers.	3.10	A	3.00	A	3.04	A	3.04	A
5. I think that a high level of usability is essential for the successful integration of AI tools into academic research workflows.	3.10	A	2.80	A	3.04	A	3.03	A
Category Mean	3.12	A	2.88	A	3.01	A	3.02	A

Table 12
Mean scores of the perceptions of the academic heads, research advisers and college students to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of Effectiveness of AI in Aiding Research

PERCEPTIONS	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The integration of Artificial Intelligence tools has a positive impact on the efficiency of research processes.	2.90	A	2.80	A	2.97	A	2.96	A
2. AI technologies contribute to a more accurate and reliable analysis of research data.	2.90	A	2.80	A	2.85	A	2.85	A
3. The use of AI in research enhances the overall quality of research outcomes.	2.80	A	2.80	A	2.96	A	2.95	A
4. AI is a valuable aid in handling complex and large datasets.	2.90	A	3.00	A	2.98	A	2.98	A
5. The application of AI tools in research is seen as beneficial for speeding up the research workflow.	3.00	A	2.80	A	3.13	A	3.11	A
Category Mean	2.90	A	2.84	A	2.98	A	2.97	A

Table 13

Mean scores of the thinking of the academic heads, research advisers and college students to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of Effectiveness of AI in Aiding Research

THINKING	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. AI is regarded as a practical and effective tool for aiding research activities.	3.10	A	2.80	A	2.96	A	2.96	A
2. The integration of AI enhances the ability to derive meaningful insights from research data.	3.10	A	2.80	A	2.96	A	2.96	A
3. The features and functionalities of AI tools align well with the needs and demands of research tasks.	3.00	A	2.80	A	2.95	A	2.95	A
4. The effectiveness of AI in aiding research is considered a crucial factor in shaping research strategies.	3.00	A	2.80	A	2.90	A	2.90	A
5. AI technologies can significantly contribute to the advancement of research methodologies.	3.10	A	2.60	A	3.01	A	3.00	A
Category Mean	3.06	A	2.76	A	2.96	A	2.96	A

Table 14

Mean scores of the opinions of the academic heads, research advisers and college students to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of Effectiveness of AI in Aiding Research

OPINIONS	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The utilization of AI tools is essential for keeping research methodologies up-to-date.	2.90	A	2.60	A	2.95	A	2.94	A
2. The effectiveness of AI in aiding research is a key factor influencing researchers' attitudes towards technology adoption.	2.80	A	3.00	A	2.98	A	2.97	A
3. AI contributes positively to the innovation and creativity in the research process.	3.00	A	3.00	A	2.96	A	2.96	A
4. The effectiveness of AI tools directly connects with the successful integration of technology into research practices.	3.00	A	2.80	A	3.01	A	3.00	A
5. The effectiveness of AI meaningfully improves the competitiveness of research endeavors.	2.90	A	3.00	A	2.96	A	2.96	A

Category Mean	2.92	A	2.88	A	2.97	A	2.97	A
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Table 15

Mean scores of the perceptions of the academic heads, research advisers and college students to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of Ease of Learning and Adaptability to AI Methodologies.

PERCEPTIONS	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The integration of Artificial Intelligence in academic research is perceived to have user-friendly interfaces for easy learning.	3.10	A	2.80	A	2.90	A	2.91	A
2. AI methodologies is found to be easily adaptable to various research tasks.	3.10	A	2.80	A	2.91	A	2.91	A
3. The learning curve for incorporating AI into research tools is perceived to be reasonable and manageable.	3.10	A	2.60	A	2.91	A	2.91	A
4. AI tools are designed with features that facilitate quick learning and adaptation.	3.00	A	2.60	A	2.97	A	2.97	A
5. AI methodologies are approachable for individuals with varying levels of technical expertise.	2.90	A	2.40	D	2.95	A	2.94	A
Category Mean	3.04	A	2.64	A	2.93	A	2.93	A

Table 16

Mean scores of the thinking of the academic heads, research advisers and college students to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of Ease of Learning and Adaptability to AI Methodologies.

THINKING	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The ease of learning AI methodologies is crucial for its successful integration into academic research practices	3.10	A	2.80	A	2.94	A	2.94	A
2. AI methodologies are adaptable to diverse research contexts.	3.00	A	2.60	A	2.90	A	2.90	A
3. AI methodologies contributes positively to the efficiency of research workflows.	3.10	A	2.60	A	2.99	A	2.99	A
4. The features and functionalities of AI tools are considered conducive to quick learning and adaptation.	3.00	A	2.60	A	2.95	A	2.95	A
5. Easy learning process for AI methodologies positively influences the overall acceptance of these tools.	3.00	A	2.80	A	3.04	A	3.03	A

Category Mean	3.04	A	2.68	A	2.97	A	2.96	A
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Table 17

Mean scores of the opinions of the academic heads, research advisers and college students to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of Ease of Learning and Adaptability to AI Methodologies.

OPINIONS	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The ease of learning and adaptability of AI tools is a key determinant of its practicality in academic research.	3.10	A	2.60	A	2.98	A	2.98	A
2. The user-friendly interfaces significantly contribute to the successful adoption of AI tools	3.20	A	2.80	A	2.95	A	2.96	A
3. The adaptability of AI tools positively impacts the creativity and innovation in research.	3.10	A	2.80	A	2.97	A	2.97	A
4. The ease of learning and adaptability of AI tools is essential for fostering a positive research environment	3.10	A	2.60	A	2.96	A	2.96	A
5. The ease of learning AI tools is crucial for enhancing research efficiency.	3.10	A	2.80	A	2.97	A	2.98	A
Category Mean	3.12	A	2.72	A	2.97	A	2.97	A

Table 18

Mean scores of the perceptions of the academic heads, research advisers and college students to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of Accuracy and Veracity of AI-Driven Outcomes.

PERCEPTIONS	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The integration of Artificial Intelligence significantly enhances the reliability and accuracy of research findings.	2.80	A	2.60	A	2.81	A	2.80	A
2. AI-driven analyses are perceived to provide more trustworthy and credible outcomes compared to traditional research methods.	2.80	A	2.60	A	2.68	A	2.69	A
3. The use of AI algorithms improves the overall accuracy and precision of research data interpretation.	2.70	A	2.60	A	2.80	A	2.79	A
4. AI-driven outcomes are perceived to minimize errors and biases in research findings.	2.80	A	2.40	D	2.78	A	2.78	A

5. The adoption of AI positively impacts the accuracy and veracity of research results and predictions.	2.80	A	2.40	D	2.88	A	2.87	A
Category Mean	2.78	A	2.52	A	2.79	A	2.78	A

Table 19

Mean scores of the thinking of the academic heads, research advisers and college students to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of Accuracy and Veracity of AI-Driven Outcomes

THINKING	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The accuracy and veracity of AI-driven outcomes are crucial factors in determining the validity of research findings.	2.80	A	2.80	A	2.88	A	2.88	A
2. AI technologies align well with the goal of achieving high accuracy and reliability in research outcomes.	2.80	A	2.80	A	2.89	A	2.88	A
3. AI has the potential to surpass traditional research methods in terms of accuracy and truthfulness.	2.80	A	2.60	A	2.83	A	2.82	A
4. The effectiveness of AI in delivering accurate outcomes is a decisive factor in embracing AI-driven research approaches.	2.90	A	3.00	A	2.88	A	2.88	A
5. AI-driven outcomes contribute significantly to enhancing the precision and trustworthiness of academic research.	2.80	A	2.60	A	2.90	A	2.89	A
Category Mean	2.82	A	2.76	A	2.87	A	2.87	A

Table 20

Mean scores of the opinions of the academic heads, research advisers and college students to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research in terms of Accuracy and Veracity of AI-Driven Outcomes

OPINIONS	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The integration of AI substantially enhances the reliability and truthfulness of research results.	2.90	A	2.40	D	2.80	A	2.80	A
2. AI-driven outcomes positively impact the credibility and reputation of research projects.	2.80	A	2.40	D	2.81	A	2.80	A
3. The accuracy and veracity of AI-driven outcomes are key determinants of the success of research endeavors.	3.00	A	2.80	A	2.84	A	2.84	A

4. AI-driven outcomes play a crucial role in generating new insights and discoveries in academic research.	2.90	A	3.00	A	2.93	A	2.93	A
5. Achieving accurate outcomes through AI technologies represents a significant advancement in the field of research.	2.90	A	2.80	A	3.00	A	2.99	A
Category Mean	2.90	A	2.68	A	2.88	A	2.87	A

Table 21
Mean scores of the advantages in in Instruction of incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) into the academic research of Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc.

Advantages in Instruction	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. AI-driven tools provide personalized learning experiences that enhance research instruction.	2.80	A	3.20	A	2.92	A	2.92	A
2. Incorporating AI in instruction helps in presenting complex research data in a more understandable format.	3.10	A	3.20	A	3.01	A	3.02	A
3. AI assists instructors in identifying and addressing individual student's research gaps efficiently.	3.00	A	3.00	A	2.98	A	2.99	A
4. AI-enabled platforms provide a diverse range of instructional materials, enhancing research education quality.	2.90	A	3.00	A	2.97	A	2.97	A
5. AI aids in real-time feedback during instructional sessions, ensuring timely guidance in research.	2.90	A	3.20	A	2.98	A	2.99	A
Category Mean	2.94	A	3.12	A	2.98	A	2.98	A

Table 22
Mean scores of the Challenges in Instruction in the incorporating of artificial intelligence (AI) into the academic research of Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc.

Challenges in Instruction	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. Integrating AI tools might make research instruction too technical for some students.	3.00	A	3.60	SA	2.85	A	2.88	A
2. Reliance on AI for instruction can diminish the human touch and mentorship crucial in research education.	3.20	A	3.80	SA	2.92	A	2.96	A
3. There's a risk of over-simplifying or misrepresenting research data	3.20	A	3.80	SA	2.99	A	3.02	A

when using AI-driven instructional tools.								
4. Keeping up with rapidly evolving AI tools can be challenging for instructors.	3.10	A	3.60	SA	2.95	A	2.97	A
5. There might be resistance or hesitancy from some instructors to incorporate AI into research instruction.	3.10	A	3.80	SA	3.03	A	3.05	A
Category Mean	3.12	A	3.72	SA	2.95	A	2.98	A

Table 23
Mean scores of the Advantages in Implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) into the academic research of Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc.

Advantages in Implementation	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. AI tools automate repetitive tasks in research implementation, increasing efficiency.	3.30	SA	3.60	SA	3.01	A	3.03	A
2. AI tools streamline and expedite research processes, leading to enhanced productivity and time management.	3.30	SA	3.60	SA	3.02	A	3.05	A
3. AI-enhanced tools foster collaboration and streamline communication during research implementation.	3.10	A	3.60	SA	2.93	A	2.95	A
4. AI tools allow for more sophisticated data visualization techniques during research presentations.	3.00	A	3.60	SA	2.87	A	2.89	A
5. Incorporating AI ensures a more consistent and standardized research implementation process.	3.00	A	3.40	SA	2.90	A	2.91	A
Category Mean	3.14	A	3.56	SA	2.94	A	2.97	A

Table 24
Mean scores of the Challenges in Implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) into the academic research of Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc.

Challenges in Implementation	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The initial setup and integration of AI tools into research can be time-consuming.	3.10	A	3.60	SA	2.75	A	2.79	A
2. Dependence on AI tools might reduce critical thinking and manual scrutiny during research implementation.	3.30	SA	3.80	SA	3.03	A	3.06	A
3. AI tools might not always align perfectly with the specific research	3.20	A	3.80	SA	3.04	A	3.06	A

methodologies used at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc.								
4. Maintaining and updating AI tools require additional resources and expertise.	3.10	A	3.60	SA	2.99	A	3.01	A
5. Ethical concerns might arise when relying heavily on AI for research implementation, especially regarding data privacy.	3.30	SA	3.80	SA	3.05	A	3.08	A
Category Mean	3.20	A	3.72	SA	2.97	A	3.00	A

Table 25
Mean scores of the advantages in evaluating of artificial intelligence (ai) into the academic research of Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc.

Advantages in Evaluation	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. AI tools provide automated and unbiased evaluation of research data.	2.90	A	3.20	A	2.94	A	2.95	A
2. AI-enhanced platforms facilitate faster feedback loops during the research evaluation phase.	2.90	A	3.40	SA	2.98	A	2.99	A
3. AI can identify patterns and correlations in research data that might be missed using traditional evaluation methods.	2.90	A	3.40	SA	2.97	A	2.98	A
4. AI-driven tools ensure a comprehensive evaluation by analyzing both quantitative and qualitative data.	2.90	A	3.20	A	3.01	A	3.00	A
5. AI enables real-time tracking of research progress, making evaluation more proactive and timelier.	2.90	A	3.20	A	2.99	A	2.99	A
Category Mean	2.90	A	3.28	SA	2.98	A	2.98	A

Table 26
Mean scores of the Challenges in evaluating of artificial intelligence (ai) into the academic research of Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc.

Challenges in Evaluation	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. Over-reliance on AI for evaluation might overlook nuanced or qualitative aspects of research.	3.10	A	3.40	SA	2.98	A	3.00	A
2. AI-driven evaluations can sometimes produce false positives or negatives.	3.20	A	3.40	SA	3.00	A	3.02	A
3. Training AI systems to evaluate research accurately requires a significant amount of accurate data.	3.40	SA	3.40	SA	3.12	A	3.14	A

4. The impersonal nature of AI evaluations might not resonate with all researchers and students.	3.30	SA	3.20	A	3.00	A	3.02	A
5. Continuous calibration and updates are necessary for AI tools to remain relevant in research evaluation.	3.30	SA	3.20	A	3.08	A	3.10	A
Category Mean	3.26	SA	3.32	SA	3.04	A	3.06	A

Table 27

Mean scores of the perceived changes of roles of academic heads in the context of AI integration into academic research

Perceived Changes in the Roles of Academic Heads	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. Academic heads are perceived to take on a more active role in setting strategic directions for AI integration in academic research.	3.00	A	2.80	A	2.99	A	2.99	A
2. The integration of AI is seen as increasing the involvement of academic heads in fostering interdisciplinary collaborations centered around AI technologies.	3.10	A	2.60	A	2.99	A	2.99	A
3. Academic heads are perceived to play a more significant role in allocating funding and resources specifically for AI-related research initiatives.	3.20	A	2.60	A	3.00	A	3.00	A
4. The integration of AI is believed to necessitate academic heads to actively engage with industry partners to stay updated on AI advancements and trends.	3.10	A	2.80	A	3.08	A	3.08	A
5. Academic heads are perceived to have an increased role in advocating for policies that promote responsible and ethical AI research practices within their institutions.	3.20	A	3.00	A	3.08	A	3.09	A
Category Mean	3.12	A	2.76	A	3.03	A	3.03	A

Table 28

Mean scores of the perceived changes of responsibilities of academic heads in the context of AI integration into academic research

Perceived Changes in the Responsibilities of Academic Heads	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. Academic heads are seen as having a responsibility to develop and implement	3.00	A	3.00	A	3.12	A	3.11	A

AI integration strategies across various academic departments.								
2. There is a perception that academic heads will be responsible for fostering a culture of continuous learning and skill development in AI among faculty members.	3.10	A	3.00	A	3.12	A	3.12	A
3. Academic heads are perceived to have a responsibility for ensuring that AI-related research projects align with the institutional mission and goals.	3.00	A	3.00	A	3.10	A	3.10	A
4. Academic heads are believed to be responsible for establishing guidelines and protocols for the ethical use of AI in academic research.	3.00	A	3.00	A	3.17	A	3.16	A
5. Academic heads are seen as having a responsibility to advocate for the recognition and promotion of faculty members who excel in AI research and innovation.	3.20	A	2.60	A	3.12	A	3.11	A
Category Mean	3.06	A	2.92	A	3.13	A	3.12	A

Table 29
Mean scores of the perceived changes of roles of research advisers in the context of AI integration into academic research

Perceived Changes in the Roles of Advisers	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. The integration of AI in academic research is perceived to increase the role of advisers in providing guidance on AI methodologies.	3.20	A	2.80	A	3.06	A	3.06	A
2. The integration of AI in academic research is seen as having an increased roles of advisers to educate students on AI technologies and their application in research.	3.20	A	3.00	A	3.06	A	3.07	A
3. The integration of AI is perceived to shift the role of advisers towards more collaborative decision-making with researchers.	3.30	SA	3.00	A	3.01	A	3.02	A
4. Advisers are perceived to play a more critical role in ensuring the quality and ethical use of AI-driven research outcomes.	3.20	A	3.20	A	3.07	A	3.08	A
5. The integration of AI is believed to necessitate advisers to take on a more strategic role in planning and incorporating AI into research projects.	3.20	A	3.00	A	3.09	A	3.10	A
Category Mean	3.22	A	3.00	A	3.06	A	3.06	A

Table 30
Mean scores of the perceived changes of Responsibilities of research advisers in the context of AI integration into academic research

Perceived Changes in the Responsibilities of advisers	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. Advisers are perceived to be responsible for initiating training programs to enhance the AI skills of research students.	3.30	SA	3.20	A	3.13	A	3.14	A
2. Advisers are seen as having a responsibility to monitor and ensure ethical practices in the use of AI in academic research.	3.30	SA	3.20	A	3.18	A	3.19	A
3. There is a perception that advisers will be responsible for allocating resources effectively to support AI-driven research initiatives.	3.30	SA	3.20	A	3.13	A	3.14	A
4. Advisers are believed to have a responsibility for continuous learning to stay updated on advancements in AI methodologies.	3.30	SA	3.20	A	3.17	A	3.18	A
5. Advisers are seen as having a responsibility to cultivate a collaborative culture that encourages the integration of AI technologies into research practices.	3.40	SA	3.00	A	3.17	A	3.18	A
Category Mean	3.32	SA	3.16	A	3.16	A	3.17	A

Table 31
Mean scores of the perceived changes of Roles of Student Researchers in the context of AI integration into academic research

Perceived Changes in the Roles of Student Researchers	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. Researchers are perceived to take on a more active role in the implementation and execution of AI methodologies in their research projects.	3.10	A	3.20	A	3.08	A	3.08	A
2. The integration of AI will encourage researchers to engage in more interdisciplinary collaboration to leverage AI knowhow.	3.10	A	3.00	A	3.07	A	3.07	A
3. Researchers are seen as having an increased role in using AI for innovative problem-solving in their respective research domains.	2.90	A	3.00	A	3.13	A	3.11	A
4. The integration of AI is perceived to shift the role of researchers towards more nuanced and critical interpretation of AI-generated data.	3.00	A	3.20	A	3.05	A	3.05	A

5. Researchers are believed to have an increased role in designing experiments that effectively incorporate AI methodologies.	3.10	A	3.00	A	3.08	A	3.08	A
Category Mean	3.04	A	3.08	A	3.08	A	3.08	A

Table 32
Mean scores of the perceived changes of Responsibilities of Student Researchers in the context of AI integration into academic research

Perceived Changes in the Responsibilities of College Students	Research Adviser		Acad. Head		Student Res.		Overall	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
1. Researchers are perceived to have a responsibility for continuous skill development in AI methodologies.	3.10	A	3.00	A	3.06	A	3.06	A
2. Researchers are seen as having a responsibility to ensure the accuracy, privacy, and security of data when using AI technologies.	3.10	A	3.00	A	3.15	A	3.14	A
3. Researchers will be responsible for adhering to ethical guidelines in the development and use of AI-driven research tools.	3.30	SA	3.00	A	3.15	A	3.15	A
4. Researchers are believed to have a responsibility for effectively communicating their AI-driven research findings to diverse audiences.	3.10	A	3.20	A	3.12	A	3.12	A
5. Researchers are perceived to be responsible for implementing quality control measures in the use of AI methodologies throughout the research process.	3.20	A	3.00	A	3.20	A	3.20	A
Category Mean	3.16	A	3.04	A	3.14	A	3.13	A

DISCUSSION

Research efforts at Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. are guided by experienced research instructors, while young student researchers actively engage in these activities. Simultaneously, seasoned academic heads shape institutional policies, including those concerning AI integration. This age diversity underscores the critical need for varied perspectives to inform decision-making regarding AI's role in the college's research endeavors.

The study revealed distinct gender distributions among respondents. Specifically, a majority of research advisers are male, suggesting a male predominance in guiding research efforts. Conversely, a higher representation of female student researchers indicates a greater engagement of females in research activities, a finding that warrants further exploration into factors such as the overall enrollment demographics at Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. Interestingly, most academic heads are also female, signifying a notable presence of female leaders influencing institutional policies. While

specific institutional data would confirm this, broader trends in academia suggest ongoing discussions about gender representation in various roles.

Research advisers and student researchers generally reported moderate familiarity with AI tools, indicating a reasonable understanding of these technologies and their potential applications in research. In contrast, academic heads predominantly expressed a "somewhat familiar" level of understanding, suggesting a basic grasp of AI tools that could influence their perceptions and opinions on AI integration in academic endeavors.

Research advisers typically possess 11-15 years of experience, demonstrating significant expertise in their field. Academic heads, however, tend to have even more extensive leadership experience, often ranging from 16-20 years. These findings highlight the seasoned and knowledgeable perspectives of both groups, which are likely to strongly influence their views on AI integration in research and academia. The general importance of experienced faculty in adopting new technologies is a well-established theme in educational technology literature.

The study underscores the critical role of advanced education in guiding student research efforts and shaping institutional policies, especially concerning AI integration in research and academic endeavors. Higher levels of education among academic leaders and research advisers equip them with the necessary knowledge and critical thinking skills to navigate the complexities of emerging technologies like AI (Holmes et al., 2023).

The variation in year levels among student respondents reflects differing approaches across college departments regarding the timing of research subjects. Some departments introduce research subjects in the fourth year, while others implement them in the third year. This distinction points to diverse academic structures and curricular designs across departments, impacting the timing of students' initial exposure to research activities. This finding is specific to OLPC's curriculum, but it aligns with the broader understanding of curriculum flexibility and varying approaches to research instruction in higher education.

Among student respondents, nursing students constituted the largest group, followed by criminology and accountancy students, reflecting the popularity of these programs at Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. While students from other colleges were also represented, their numbers were smaller, likely due to fewer students from those departments currently enrolled in research for the Academic Year 2023-2024. This data represents a specific finding of this study and reflects the unique demographic composition of the institution.

Academic heads, research advisers, and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc. reported their initial experiences and learning regarding AI tools in the research setting. Respondents expressed a strong belief in the significant benefits of incorporating AI tools into academic projects, even if AI is not yet formally integrated into the curriculum. They also highlighted a clear need for more structured guidance and

training during their initial encounters with AI in research. Interestingly, respondents frequently mentioned that their first exposure to AI tools for research occurred through online resources provided by the college.

A positive perception exists among research advisers, academic heads, and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc., regarding the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research, particularly concerning the usability of AI tools. Research advisers concurred that AI tool design contributes to a positive user experience, while academic heads strongly agreed on the intuitiveness of AI tool interfaces. College students similarly expressed agreement on the positive impact of AI tool design on user experience and its overall usability in academic research. These findings underscore the importance of user-friendly AI tool design in enhancing the effectiveness of academic research, highlighting the potential benefits of AI integration in academic endeavors.

A shared belief among research advisers, academic heads, and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc., centers on the potential benefits of integrating artificial intelligence (AI) in academic research, specifically focusing on the usability of AI tools. Research advisers emphasized the importance of easy learning and adaptation to AI tool functionalities for effective use in research. Academic heads supported the modernization and optimization of research processes through AI tools, highlighting their positive impact on decision-making. College students also stressed the significance of easy learning and adaptation to AI tools for effective research. Overall, the findings indicate that AI tools have the potential to enhance research processes, improve decision-making, and positively impact academic endeavors at the institution.

The study revealed a consensus on the positive impact of user-friendly artificial intelligence (AI) tools on academic research productivity. Research advisers emphasized the crucial role of user-friendly design in enhancing overall research efficiency. Academic heads also recognized the significance of user-friendly AI tools, highlighting their practicality and ease of use in driving researcher acceptance. Similarly, student researchers acknowledged the importance of user-friendly AI tools in enhancing research productivity. Overall, the findings underscore the consensus that prioritizing usability in AI tool design is essential for optimizing research outcomes and fostering acceptance and effectiveness in academic research endeavors (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

A shared perception exists among research advisers, academic heads, and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc., regarding the effectiveness of artificial intelligence (AI) in aiding academic research. Research advisers believe that AI tools accelerate the research workflow, indicating their recognition of AI's efficiency in research processes. Academic heads view AI as valuable for handling complex datasets, highlighting its potential in managing large and intricate research data. Similarly, student researchers acknowledge the benefits of AI in expediting the research workflow. Overall, the findings indicate a consensus perception among respondents that AI tools play a beneficial role in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of academic

research endeavors, reflecting a positive perception towards AI integration in research practices.

Research advisers agreed that AI is perceived as a practical and effective tool for research activities, enhancing the ability to derive meaningful insights from research data and contributing significantly to the advancement of research methodologies. Academic heads similarly believe that AI is practical and effective for research, aligning well with research needs and demands, and considering AI's effectiveness crucial in shaping research strategies. Student researchers also agreed that AI can significantly contribute to research methodologies. Overall, respondents believe that AI technologies hold great potential in advancing research methodologies, highlighting the perceived benefits of AI integration in academic research endeavors.

Research advisers and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc. largely agree on integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into academic research. Research advisers concur that AI boosts innovation and creativity in research, and its effectiveness is vital for technology integration in research. Academic heads believe AI's effectiveness impacts researchers' technology adoption and enhances creativity in research. Student researchers also agreed on the importance of AI's effectiveness for successful technology integration. Overall, in the opinions of respondents, AI's effectiveness is crucial for smoothly integrating technology into research practices, promoting innovation and creativity (Al-Samarraie & Ghazal, 2024a).

Respondents generally agreed that AI tools are easy to learn and adapt to. Research advisers and academic heads found AI interfaces user-friendly and AI methods adaptable to various tasks. Students felt AI tools were quick to learn and use. These findings suggest a positive perception towards integrating AI into academic research, indicating that the perceived accessibility of AI contributes to its potential adoption.

Respondents widely believe that AI tools need to be easy to learn and adapt to. Research advisers emphasized this point, stating it's crucial for successful integration and improves research efficiency. Academic heads and students shared this view, emphasizing that an easy learning process for AI tools is essential for their overall acceptance. These findings demonstrate a shared understanding among all respondents that easy learning and adaptability are key for AI tools to be accepted in academic research, highlighting the importance of user-friendly AI technologies in advancing research.

Academic heads, research advisers, and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc., hold consistent opinions about using Artificial Intelligence (AI) in academic research during 2023-2024. Both research advisers and academic heads agreed that user-friendly interfaces are crucial for adopting AI tools successfully. Academic heads also believe that adaptable AI tools boost creativity in research. All groups stressed that AI tools need to be easy to learn for research efficiency. Student researchers also agreed that easy learning and adaptability are key for AI tools to be

practical in research. There is a universal recognition of the importance of user-friendly interfaces and adaptable AI methods for making AI useful in academic research.

Academic heads, research advisers, and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc., all agree that integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) improves the reliability and accuracy of research outcomes. Research advisers believe AI enhances credibility compared to traditional methods and reduces errors and biases. Academic heads echoed this, emphasizing AI's role in improving data interpretation. College students also view AI as positively impacting research accuracy. Overall, in the perception of respondents, AI adoption improves research credibility and accuracy, showing its importance in academic research (Koussa & Al-Taani, 2024).

Academic heads, research advisers, and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc. all agree that the accuracy of AI-driven outcomes is crucial for embracing AI in research. Research advisers pointed out that accurate AI outcomes are decisive for adopting AI-driven research. Academic heads and student researchers emphasized the significant contribution of AI-driven outcomes to enhancing research precision and trustworthiness. Overall, respondents believe that AI's ability to deliver accurate outcomes is key to improving research quality and reliability, indicating a positive outlook towards integrating AI into academic research practices (Mollick & Mollick, 2023).

Academic heads, research advisers, and student researchers at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc. all agree that accurate AI-driven outcomes are crucial for research success. Research advisers emphasize this, while academic heads highlight the role of AI in generating new insights. Students also see accurate AI outcomes as a significant step forward in research. Overall, the opinion of respondents is that achieving accurate outcomes through AI is a significant advancement in research (Russell & Norvig, 2010).

Academic heads, research advisers, and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc. all agree that incorporating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into research instruction has distinct advantages. They believe it aids in presenting complex data in a more understandable way. Academic heads emphasize personalized learning experiences and real-time feedback, with student researchers also recognizing these benefits. Overall, respondents agree that using AI in instruction makes complex research data easier to understand (Chen et al., 2023).

Academic heads, research advisers, and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc. share a common stance on the challenges of incorporating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into research instruction. Respondents are concerned that over-reliance on AI could diminish the personal touch and mentorship crucial for research education. There's also a perceived risk of oversimplifying or misrepresenting research data with AI-driven tools. Furthermore, student researchers agree that there might be potential resistance from some instructors to use AI in research instruction. Overall, respondents agree that instructor resistance could be a significant challenge in integrating AI into research instruction (Kintu & Kizito, 2024; Channa & Kanna, 2025).

Research advisers, academic heads, and student researchers all agree that AI tools offer significant benefits such as automating repetitive tasks, streamlining research processes, and enhancing productivity. They further noted that AI facilitates collaboration, improves communication, and enables sophisticated data visualization during research presentations. Overall, respondents agree that AI enhances efficiency, productivity, and time management in research implementation (Al-Samarraie & Ghazal, 2023).

The study identified several challenges in integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into academic research at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan. Research advisers, academic heads, and student researchers concurred that excessive reliance on AI might reduce critical thinking and manual scrutiny during research. They also expressed ethical concerns, particularly regarding data privacy, including issues such as unauthorized access to data, data breaches, and the potential misuse of data. When relying heavily on AI for research implementation, there is a recognized risk that sensitive data could be compromised, leading to privacy violations (Hussain & Khan, 2025; Channa & Kanna, 2025).

Research advisers, academic heads, and student researchers at Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. recognize that AI offers several advantages in academic research evaluation. These include automated and unbiased evaluation of research data, faster feedback loops, improved identification of patterns and correlations in data, comprehensive analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data, and real-time tracking of research progress. This consensus highlights the potential of AI to enhance the quality, efficiency, and comprehensiveness of academic research evaluation processes (Baker & Siemens, 2014).

The study explored the challenges in integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into academic research evaluation at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan for the Academic Year 2023-2024. Research advisers emphasize the difficulty of training AI systems accurately due to the need for a substantial amount of precise data. Academic heads and student researchers agree, noting additional challenges such as the risk of overlooking nuanced aspects of research and the potential for AI-driven evaluations to produce false results. Overall, respondents agree that incorporating AI into research evaluation poses challenges, particularly regarding the acquisition of accurate data and the limitations of AI in capturing qualitative aspects of research (Holstein et al., 2017).

Research advisers agree that academic heads are increasingly responsible for allocating funds and advocating for policies promoting ethical AI research. Academic heads themselves concurred, acknowledging their increased role in advocating for responsible AI practices. Similarly, student researchers recognized academic heads' need to engage with industry partners and promote ethical AI research. Overall, respondents agree that AI integration requires academic heads to take on more responsibility in funding allocation, policy advocacy, and collaboration with industry partners to ensure ethical AI practices within the institution (Alharbi & Baporikar, 2024).

The responsibilities of academic heads at Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. are perceived to change significantly with the integration of Artificial

Intelligence (AI) into academic research for the Academic Year 2023-2024. Research advisers agreed that academic heads are now seen as advocates for recognizing and promoting faculty, which could involve highlighting faculty members' research accomplishments, promoting their work to external stakeholders, and advocating for their professional development and advancement opportunities. Academic heads themselves concurred, acknowledging new responsibilities such as developing AI integration strategies, fostering a culture of learning in AI, ensuring research aligns with institutional goals, and establishing ethical guidelines for AI use. Student researchers also agreed, emphasizing the need for academic heads to set ethical standards for AI research. Overall, there's a shared belief that AI integration requires academic heads to take on more roles in strategic planning, learning culture, and ethical practices within the institution concerning research equipped with AI tools (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

Research advisers agreed that AI integration shifts their role towards more collaborative decision-making with researchers, emphasizing a team-oriented approach to decision-making. Academic heads noted that advisers are now seen as having a more critical role in ensuring the quality and ethical use of AI-driven research outcomes, highlighting the importance of their oversight in maintaining research integrity. Student researchers also agreed, believing that AI integration requires advisers to adopt a more strategic role in planning and incorporating AI into research projects, indicating a need for advisers to lead in integrating AI effectively. Overall, respondents agree that AI integration prompts research advisers to engage in collaborative decision-making, ensure research quality and ethics, and take a strategic approach to AI incorporation into research projects (Kaddoura, 2025).

The responsibilities of research advisers at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan are perceived to change with the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into academic research for the Academic Year 2023-2024. Research advisers strongly agreed that they need to create a collaborative culture supporting the use of AI in research. Academic heads agree and add that advisers should also initiate training programs to improve students' AI skills, ensure ethical AI use, allocate resources effectively, and continuously learn about AI advancements. Student researchers also agree that advisers should monitor and ensure ethical AI practices. Overall, there's a consensus that advisers' roles expand to include fostering collaboration, training students, ensuring ethics, allocating resources well, and staying updated on AI advancements (Khan & Khan, 2023).

With the integration of AI into academic research, students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan Inc. are expected to become more independent in their research. They will play a more active role in using AI techniques, collaborating across disciplines, and interpreting AI-generated data critically. This means they may rely less on their advisers for certain aspects of their research, as they gain proficiency in using AI. Overall, AI integration is seen as empowering students to take charge of their research projects and solve problems creatively with AI (Holmes et al., 2019).

The perceived changes in the responsibilities of student researchers at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into

academic research for the Academic Year 2023-2024 are significant. Research advisers believe that students will be responsible for adhering to ethical guidelines when developing and using AI-driven research tools. Academic heads, on the other hand, think that students will have a responsibility to effectively communicate their AI-driven research findings to diverse audiences. Student researchers themselves agreed that they will be responsible for implementing quality control measures in the use of AI methodologies throughout the research process. Overall, there's a shared expectation that students will take on additional responsibilities related to ethics, communication, and quality control as they engage with AI in their research endeavors (Sembiring & Simatupang, 2025; Buchanan, 2023).

Conclusions

The study was found to have deep into the thoughts of academic heads, research advisers, and college students at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc. regarding the incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) into research and academics during the academic year 2023-2024. The response of the respondents is clear, AI holds huge promise for improving research and academic endeavors. However, alongside this optimism, there's a tangible concern about potential ethical implications, particularly regarding data privacy and the risk of diminishing critical thinking skills with excessive reliance on AI. What's striking is how roles and responsibilities are evolving in response to AI integration. Academic heads are now expected to play a more active role in securing funding, advocating for policy changes, and fostering collaboration with industry partners to ensure ethical AI practices. Likewise, research advisers are being called upon to engage in more collaborative decision-making, uphold research quality and ethics, and provide guidance and training to students. On the student side, there's a sense of empowerment stemming from AI's potential to enhance problem-solving skills and research capabilities. However, there's also a recognition of the need for additional support and guidance to navigate the complexities of AI integration effectively. While the study underscores the transformative potential of AI in academia, it also emphasizes the importance of addressing ethical concerns and providing comprehensive support and guidance to ensure that students and stakeholders can harness the benefits of AI while mitigating potential risks. This complex understanding will undoubtedly inform future strategies for integrating AI into research and academic practices, not only at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc. but also across similar institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion and findings, the researcher recommends the following:

1. Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. should promote the incorporation of AI tools and methodologies into research processes across all academic disciplines.
2. There must be a structured framework outlining the integration of AI tools into the curriculum, research processes, and institutional policies. This framework should address ethical considerations, data privacy, and faculty development.

3. Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. should provide extensive training and development programs to equip faculty members with the necessary skills to effectively integrate AI into their teaching and research. This includes workshops on AI tools, data analysis, and ethical considerations.
4. Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. should form a dedicated committee to develop and implement ethical guidelines for AI use in research and education. This committee will oversee data privacy, algorithmic fairness, and responsible AI practices.
5. Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. should allocate sufficient resources for acquiring necessary hardware, software, and digital infrastructure to support AI integration. This includes high-performance computing facilities and access to relevant databases.
6. Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc. should encourage collaboration between faculty, students, and industry partners to accelerate AI adoption and knowledge sharing. Partnerships can facilitate access to expertise, resources, and real-world applications of AI.
7. Proposed Policy and Guidelines for the Integration of Artificial Intelligence in Research at Our Lady of the Pillar College - Cauayan, Inc:

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author hereby declares that this study, titled "PERCEPTIONS AND OPINIONS ON THE INTEGRATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN RESEARCH AND ACADEMICS: BASIS FOR POLICY DEVELOPMENT" was conducted in full compliance with ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, who were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained, and their well-being was safeguarded throughout the research process. The author further declares that no conflict of interest influenced the conduct of this study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all findings were interpreted objectively and without bias. Lastly, the results of this study were utilized solely for academic and research purposes.

Acknowledgments

The researcher extends profound gratitude to the Almighty Father for bestowing the wisdom, knowledge, and strength necessary to complete this study. Sincere appreciation is also extended to the following individuals whose unwavering support, encouragement, and assistance significantly contributed to the successful completion of this research:

To Dr. Exuperio V. Flores, Jr., School President of Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc., for his continuous motivation and encouragement. His trust in the researcher's abilities and his support—especially through opportunities to attend seminars related to artificial intelligence—greatly enriched the depth of this study.

To all the respondents, including academic heads, research advisers, and student researchers of Our Lady of the Pillar College – Cauayan, Inc., heartfelt thanks are given for their time and participation. Their willingness to respond to the survey made this research endeavor possible.

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